

Direct Calculation of Radial Band Structures in Circular Gratings via a Generalized Bloch Condition

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Abstract: Concentric circular gratings are classic optical elements that are critical to engineer light-matter interactions in the form of bullseye cavities, annulus cavities, and circular Bragg resonators. However, due to the absence of translational symmetry, calculating their band structure along the radial direction has remained challenging. In this paper, we introduce a physically intuitive generalized radial Bloch condition for cylindrical systems, mathematically prove it, and use it to build the eigenvalue equation for circular gratings. Energy bands of the circular grating with a Hankel wave period are computed using the transfer matrix method. The approach has been validated against experimental data. And reflectance spectra of annulus cavities and field distribution of resonance modes are studied. It is shown that these properties are highly related to the energy bands along the radial direction. This work provides a direct, intuitive, and computationally efficient method to analyze and design complex circular grating devices, resolving a persistent bottleneck in the modeling of these critical photonic components.

1. Introduction

Concentric circular gratings (CCG) possess a long history and are widely used in fundamental research and industrial manufacturing[1]. Bullseye cavities can manipulate quantum quantum emitters via the Purcell effect to improve light collection efficiency, leading to their employment in single photon sources[2–5]. Circular Bragg[6–8] and annulus Bragg defect mode resonators[9–11] can reduce both line width and threshold gain of lasers, achieving single mode lasing. Furthermore, diffraction from second-order circular distributed feedback (DFB) structures generates surface emitting lasers, which have been demonstrated across different frequency regimes from ultraviolet to terahertz using different materials[12–17]. CCG also function effectively as optical filters[18] and couplers[19].

Despite their prevalence in nanophotonic, optoelectronics, direct studies on the radial dispersion relation of CCG remain scarce. Typically, CCG with a Hankel wave “period” (referred to as pseudo-period) are approximated as 1D DFB or distributed Bragg reflector (DBR). However, noticeable differences exist in the spatial distribution of refractive index and propagating waves between Cartesian and cylindrical geometries. As previously noted by Amnon Yariv, a direct analysis of CCG faces a fundamental hurdle: there is no direct equivalent to the Bloch’s theorem in the cylindrical system[20]. This persistent theoretical gap has forced researchers to rely on either cumbersome formalism[21] or computationally intensive numerical simulations such as FDTD[18].

To address this long-standing bottleneck, this paper introduces a generalized radial Bloch condition for cylindrical systems. This condition provides the necessary closure relationship to calculate the radial band structure. We utilize the transfer matrix method (TMM) to calculate the dispersion relation, offering a physically insightful alternative to brute-force methods.

2. Radial Transfer Matrix Formalism

To establish the formal problem, without loss of generality, we utilize the Helmholtz equation in cylindrical coordinate for electric or magnetic field, depending on whether the system supports TM or TE modes[6,22].

$$\left[\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \right) + \frac{1}{\rho^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \varphi^2} + k_0^2 \varepsilon(\rho, z) + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \right] U(\rho, \varphi, z) = 0 \quad (1)$$

Under the assumption that the radius (ρ or r), azimuth (φ), and height (z) directions are separable, the field U can be written as the product of three functions according to the method of separation of variables.

$$U(\rho, \varphi, z) = R(\rho)M(\varphi)Z(z) \quad (2)$$

Thanks to the radial symmetry of CCG, the angular component is a complex exponential of the azimuth angle, where m is a non-negative integer representing the azimuthal order.

$$M(\varphi) = e^{im\varphi} \quad (3)$$

Along the height direction, the field distribution satisfies the following Eigen equation, where β is the modal wave vector of waves propagating radially.

$$\left[k_0^2 \varepsilon(\rho, z) + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \right] Z(z) = \beta^2 Z(z) \quad (4)$$

The radial function is governed by the Bessel equation.

$$\left[\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \right) + \beta^2 - \frac{m^2}{\rho^2} \right] R(\rho) = 0 \quad (5)$$

The solutions are Bessel functions of the first and the second kind. Alternatively, they can be written as Hankel functions of the first (H_1) and the second (H_2) kind, corresponding to the outward and inward propagating waves along the radial axis. For a CCG, the radius is divided into discrete sections of different wave vectors. Thus the field distribution is a piecewise function[23] defined by complex amplitudes A_i and B_i .

$$R_i(\rho) = A_i * H_1(m, \beta_i \rho) + B_i * H_2(m, \beta_i \rho) \quad (6)$$

Unlike the TMM for plane waves, the complex amplitudes are bonded with Hankel functions within each section and are position-dependent. Thus, there is no need to calculate a propagation matrix. The interface matrix can be built from the continuation of field, and its first order derivatives at each side of the section interface.

For an electric field, the equation ensures the magnetic field parallel to the interface is continuous.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} R(\rho_+) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} R(\rho_-) \quad (7)$$

For a magnetic field, the equation ensures the electric field parallel to the interface is continuous.

$$\frac{1}{\varepsilon(\rho_+, z)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} R(\rho_+) = \frac{1}{\varepsilon(\rho_-, z)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} R(\rho_-) \quad (8)$$

Thus the interface matrix that links both sides can be obtained, and written in the following form.

$$\begin{pmatrix} A_{i+1} \\ B_{i+1} \end{pmatrix} = M_i \begin{pmatrix} A_i \\ B_i \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

With the interface matrix (M_i) for each interface, the complex amplitudes along the radius can be calculated, similar to the TMM for plane waves[24].

3. The Generalized Radial Bloch Condition

To solve for the dispersion relation, a closure relationship analogous to Bloch's theorem is required. For a 1D Cartesian photonic crystal, Bloch's theorem, $\Psi(x+T) = e^{ikT}\Psi(x)$, establishes that an eigen mode (a Bloch wave) must transform by a simple phase factor across one unit cell. The phase factor, e^{ikT} , is precisely the propagator for a plane wave, which is the eigen mode of a uniform medium, across the same distance.

We extend this physical principle to the cylindrical system. In a uniform cylindrical medium, the eigen modes are not plane waves but Hankel waves, such as $H_1(m, \beta_{\text{eff}})$. We therefore postulate the condition for an eigen mode in a pseudo-periodic circular grating: the wave field across one unit cell (from radius ρ_i to ρ_{i+N}) must transform in the same manner as a Hankel wave propagating in an effective uniform medium. The propagator for a pure Hankel wave from ρ_i to ρ_{i+N} is the ratio $H_1(m, \beta_{\text{eff}}\rho_{i+N})/H_1(m, \beta_{\text{eff}}\rho_i)$. This lead to our generalized radial Bloch condition.

$$R(\rho_{i+N}) = \frac{H_1(m, \beta_{\text{eff}}\rho_{i+N})}{H_1(m, \beta_{\text{eff}}\rho_i)} R(\rho_i) \quad (10)$$

Where β_{eff} is the effective Bloch wave vector of the system.

This condition accounts for the amplitude decay and phase evolution inherent to cylindrical waves, features absent in the Cartesian case. In essence, it means that for a given point on the energy bands, the complex wave in the grating propagates, on average, like a pure Hankel wave in an effective uniform medium.

The rigorous mathematical derivation of Equation (10) is provided in the Supplement. We demonstrate that for ideal conformal circular gratings that utilize both placement and contrast modulation, the effective potential is strictly periodic, and the generalized radial Bloch condition applies. Conversely, for standard gratings with pseudo-period Hankel wave, which satisfy placement modulation but maintain a constant refractive index contrast, the Bloch condition serves as a robust adiabatic approximation. In such structures, the uncompensated index contrast introduces a residual potential error that scales as $O(1/\rho^2)$, allowing the radial band structure to be modeled with a predictable and estimable error.

The validity of this condition will be demonstrated through consistency checks and comparison with experimental data in the following sections.

4. Radial Band Structure and Parametric Analysis

III-nitrides are famous light-emitting materials covering a broad spectrum range. The CCG under investigation is a GaN slab with gratings on one side[12]. The top and bottom claddings are air. As shown in Figure 1, the top view of the CCG resembles the cross-sectional image of a Bragg fiber. In a fiber light is guided and travels in the z direction, so dispersion along the z axis is of interest. Here in the CCG, light is guided by the refractive contrast in the z direction, and propagates along the r (or ρ) direction. The circular gratings diffract and couple the inward and outward traveling Hankel waves. If the arrangement of the grating meets the pseudo-period of Hankel functions, an energy gap opens where the coupling is strong in wave vector space.

To facilitate further analysis, the CCG is divided into two kinds of sections (or rings) according to the position of gratings, i.e., the air ring and the GaN ring, depending on the materials in the top view. The steps to design the CCG are as follows. (1) Solve the eigen equation (Equation 4) in the height direction for the air and GaN rings for a given wavelength, and obtain the modal index in each ring. (2) Add air and GaN rings alternatively with width given in nodes (zeros) of Bessel functions. The pseudo-period of the CCG is 4 nodes. (3)

Scale the width of each section using its modal index of the fundamental z-mode. This procedure ensures that the CCG works for a specific wavelength.

The slab thickness t is 200 nm. The GaN height h varies and is set to 20 nm by default. The CCG is designed for fundamental height and azimuth mode for a vacuum wavelength of 420 nm. The air rings align with the nodes of Bessel functions and have a width (optical length) of one quarter pseudo-period. The center disk has a radius of one-eighth pseudo-period. The default unit cell is ring 100 and 101 (referred to as 100-101). If not mentioned otherwise, these parameters will be used to calculate bands.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of a CCG made of GaN and air. (a) Top view. (b) Sectional view, the rings (or sections), and the interfaces coordinates are labeled.

Figure 2. The height modes. (a) The electric field profiles of fundamental and first order mode along the height (z) direction. The first order modes are shifted upward. The solid (dash) line is

for the GaN (Air) ring. (b) Dispersion relation in the radius direction for different height modes near the gamma point.

Bands near the gamma point for both fundamental and first order z-modes are calculated, shown in Figure 2. Because the GaN ring is thicker than the air ring in the z direction, its field profile is slightly wider, and its modal index is larger. Compared to the fundamental modes, the first modes have smaller values and larger contrast of modal index, thus its bands are in the short wavelength range and has a wider gap. It is worth noting that, during the calculation of energy bands, an assumption has been made implicitly. The gratings only cause a small perturbation to modes in the GaN slab as shown in Figure 2(a), thus one z-mode will not be diffracted into the other z-modes. Since the CCG is designed for fundamental z-modes, the following context will focus on bands for fundamental z-mode only.

Figure 3. Effects of different grating height h . The CCG for each h is built with the mode refractive index of GaN ring (section) taken into consideration. (a) The ratio of mode refractive index of GaN section to Air section for fundamental modes. (b) Energy bands near gamma point for h of different values from 0 to 50 nm. The two lines near the band edges are for eyes only.

The height of the gratings affects the dispersion relation by altering the mode refractive index contrast in the air and GaN rings. As shown in Figure 3(a), the mode refractive index ratio, defined by the mode refractive index of the GaN ring to the air ring, increases with the grating height h from zero when there is no grating. Consequently, the band gap increases monotonously with h in Figure 3(b). The gamma points also shift to the side of larger wave vector. Attention has to be paid to the question that to what extent the TMM is still applicable. First, if h is too large, different z modes in GaN and air sections will interact and mix. Second, in the TMM, z direction is decoupled from the radial direction, which is not valid if h is comparable to thickness t . In this work, h is selected to be 20 nm, which is large enough to yield a distinct band gap, while keeping the relative refractive index difference less than 1% between the air and GaN section.

Figure 4. Energy bands computed with 8 unit cell taken at different locations. An odd number indicates an air section while even number means a GaN section. Two adjacent rings form a unit cell. It is noted that the bands for the 8 unit cells are the same, so only the bands for 1000-1001 is visible.

The Hankel function is not periodic along the radial direction, especially near the center. Bloch theorem fails as a consequence. An asymptotic formula, for instance a complex exponential function divided by square root of radius, cannot capture the pseudo-period of the Hankel wave. To verify whether the eigen equation (Equation 10) works as expected, energy bands computed using unit cells at different radial positions are shown in Figure 4. They are not distinguishable from each other, no matter if the calculation is for a unit cell near or away from the center, starting from a GaN ring or an air ring. The eigen equation in this paper indeed captures the “period” nature of Hankel waves.

Figure 5. Energy bands computed using 4 different number of unit cells starting from section 1000. The number of unit cell is 1, 3, 9, and 32 for the plots. (a) bands near the first gamma point. The bands are the same for the 4 cases, so only the bands for 1000-1065 is visible. (b) bands in large scale.

For a 1D Bragg grating, the reciprocal lattice is inversely proportional to the period. To further test the analogy with 1D periodic systems, we investigated the effect of using a supercell (multiple unit cells treated as one larger cell). In Figure 5(a), near the gamma point, the dispersion relation is indistinguishable regardless of the number of unit cells. As the supercell gets bigger, the effective Brillouin zone shrinks accordingly. In Figure 5(b), the width of the Brillouin zone is 0.0360, 0.0120, 0.0040, and 0.0011 nm^{-1} for unit cells of 1, 3, 9, and 32, respectively. Multiple bands appear within a smaller range due to the band folding effect. In brief, the Hankel waves truly share translational symmetry related properties even though they are not periodic along the radius direction.

Figure 6. Dispersion relation for different azimuthal orders computed using unit cells at different locations. (a) The unit cell is 10-11 for azimuthal order of 0 and 1. (b) The unit cell is 100-101 for azimuthal order of 0 and 1. The bands are the same, so only bands for azimuthal order of 1 is visible. (c) The unit cell is 100-101 for azimuthal orders from 0 to 50.

A unique characteristic of the Hankel wave is that it is azimuthal order dependent. The azimuthal order m appears in the Bessel equation, and has a direct effect on the nodes on the Hankel waves. And as the radius increases, the m containing term diminishes quickly. In a CCG designed for fundamental azimuthal order ($m = 0$), how the high order Hankel wave behaves is important, especially for lasers, because m will determine the number of lobes in the far field. In Figure 6(a) and 6(b), bands are shown for m of 0, 1 for the unit cells at different radial positions. Near the center of the CCG, the bands for $m = 1$ seem shifted along the right-bottom branch, while the gap remains unchanged. Away from the CCG center, the bands overlap with each other. It is confirmed that the large radius will reduce the weight of m in the Bessel equation thus the differences between different m disappear. In Figure 6(c), bands for very large m are shown. The bands are all shifted along the right-bottom branch, but with very uneven displacement. As detailed in the error estimation section of the supplement, this positive shift in both frequency and wave vector stems from the uncompensated refractive index contrast inherent to standard Hankel-phased gratings. The shift increases

rapidly for larger m due to the m^2 dependence, but diminishes at larger radii as the $1/\rho^2$ term forces the residual potential to vanish.

5. Validation against Experimental Result

Figure 7. Measured energy bands of an HfO₂ CCG filter (contour using extracted data from literature[18]) and calculated using our TMM for TE and TM modes (lines).

To validate the predictive power of our method, a comparison between measured data and computed bands is shown in Figure 7. In the measurements, the angle of incidence determines the in-plane wave vector, which directly probes the photonic bands. In the calculation of band structure, real device parameters are used. The CCG optical filter is made of 200 nm thick suspended HfO₂[18], whose refractive index is set as 1.89 which is the value at 650 nm from a public database. While the referenced experiment uses a grating with a fixed 500 nm period, at radius of a few wavelengths, the local pseudo-period of a Hankel wave becomes nearly constant, allowing for a direct comparison. Therefore, our calculation was performed using unit cell 20-21, corresponding to a radius of approximately 5 μm (half of radius of the CCG in the literature). As seen in Figure 7, both the TE bands and the TM bands agree excellently with the measured data. In the literature[18], FDTD simulation is used to evaluate the measure bands. In contrast, our method offers a computationally effective and physically incisive alternative. It suggests that the combination of radial Bloch condition with TMM is of practical usage in analyzing real-world devices. Our method has also been successfully applied to calculate band structure of a Hankel phased CCG fabricated on ITO/GaN sample[25].

6. Application in Annulus Cavity Resonance

Figure 8. Resonance in an annulus cavity from section 100 to 300. Only rings within this range are considered. (a) Reflectance and transmittance of amplitudes of inward propagating Hankel wave at section 300. The inset schematically shows the annulus cavity. (b) Electric field profiles at different resonance wavelengths.

If there are the gratings only within a radius range, outside which is mere GaN slab, the CCG becomes an annulus cavity. Hankel waves guided by the slab interfere and resonate within this cavity, like plane waves in a Fabry-Perot resonator. When a Hankel wave travels into the annulus cavity from the large radius side, part of the light will be reflected and part will go into the cavity and exit at the small radius side. The reflectance and transmittance of amplitudes are shown in Figure 8(a). It is noted that at the 420 nm, the dip in transmittance is due to the band gap. There are 3 resonance points on each side of the gap, all of which are on the band edges of the bottom and top branches of the energy bands. It is easy to tell that they are 0th, 1st and 2nd order cavity modes by their offset from the peak of reflectance. It can be verified that the product of the cavity width and their corresponding offset of wave vector from gamma point in band diagram equals to π , 2π , and 3π , respectively. Figure 8(b) shows the electric field profiles at the top branches of the energy band. As expected, there is 0, 1, and 2 nodes in profiles for incidence wavelength of 422.2nm, 424.3nm, 426.4nm, respectively. The robustness of these resonance modes can be mathematically justified using the error estimation framework established in the Supplement. The residual potential, which arises from the uncompensated curvature in standard gratings, acts as an additive energy barrier in the radial wave equation. This leads to a predictable positive frequency shift in the resonance modes, scaling as $(m^2 - 1/4)/\rho$.

7. Discussion

While the generalized radial Bloch condition together with TMM provides a powerful analytical framework, its limitations should be acknowledged. Because our TMM approach relies on the separation of variables, it must be applied cautiously to structures with large

grating heights. For structures with very deep gratings, h is comparable to the slab thickness t , coupling between different z -modes becomes significant, and a full 2D or 3D simulation will be required. Nevertheless, for a wide range of practical devices, our method remains an accurate and computationally inexpensive alternative.

Furthermore, the use of solid-state terminology, such as "gamma point" and "Brillouin zone", is applied by analogy. While the CCG lacks true translational symmetry, the grating structure is designed to have a pseudo-periodicity matched to the nodes of the Hankel functions. This matching creates coherent back-scattering that opens a band gap, similar to a 1D DBR. The concepts of band folding and reciprocal lattice space are therefore provide highly useful interpretive framework, even if they are not rigorously defined in the same way as for a Cartesian crystal.

The primary contribution of this work is the introduction and mathematical derivation of the generalized Bloch condition, paired with a physically grounded, highly efficient method for calculating the radial band structure of CCG. Our method bridges the critical gap between overly simplistic 1D analogies and computationally prohibitive full-wave simulations, providing the much-needed physical insight that is often obscured in brute-force numerical methods. It provides direct insight into the dispersion and band gap properties, enabling the intuitive and rapid design of CCG-based devices such as filters, resonators[25], and surface-emitting lasers[26].

Beyond the generalized Bloch condition, the supplement proves an even more profound physical picture that the waves propagating in CCG can be described by a Hankel function modulated by periodic envelop. This serves as the cylindrical counterpart to the Bloch's theorem for 1D periodic dielectric stack. Recently, FDTD and Hankel transform have been used to calculate photonic band structure in CCG[27]. It has been demonstrated both numerically and experimentally that the energy gaps are created when the outward and inward propagating waves couple.

8. Conclusion

In summary, we have introduced and rigorously derived a generalized radial Bloch condition for Hankel waves in cylindrical coordinate systems. By establishing the appropriate eigenvalue equation, we successfully calculated the radial energy bands of CCG structures using a modified TMM, operating under the assumption that the electromagnetic fields can be decoupled along the height and radial axes. We found that the radial dispersion relation of Hankel waves closely resembles that of plane waves in a 1D photonic crystal. The azimuthal order m causes the energy bands to shift toward shorter wavelengths and larger wave vectors; this effect scales with the order number but diminishes rapidly at large radii. The theoretical framework was robustly validated against experimental data from the literature. Furthermore, applying our TMM method to an annular resonator revealed that the radial dispersion relation profoundly governs the optical properties of such cavity devices. Ultimately, this work provides a powerful, intuitive, and mathematically sound framework for analyzing and designing devices based on circular gratings, successfully overcoming the long-standing theoretical challenge posed by their lack of Cartesian translational symmetry.

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Data Availability. Data underlying the results presented in this paper are not publicly available at this time but may be obtained from the authors upon reasonable request.

Supplementary Document. See Supplement 1 for supporting content.

Reference

1. M. C. King and D. H. Berry, "Photolithographic Mask Alignment Using Moiré Techniques," *Appl. Opt.*, **AO 11**(11), 2455–2459 (1972).
2. L. Li, E. H. Chen, J. Zheng, S. L. Mouradian, F. Dolde, T. Schröder, S. Karaveli, M. L. Markham, D. J. Twitchen, and D. Englund, "Efficient Photon Collection from a Nitrogen Vacancy Center in a Circular Bullseye Grating," *Nano Lett.* **15**(3), 1493–1497 (2015).
3. M. Meunier, J. J. H. Eng, Z. Mu, S. Chenot, V. Brändli, P. de Mierry, W. Gao, and J. Zúñiga-Pérez, "Telecom single-photon emitters in GaN operating at room temperature: embedment into bullseye antennas," *Nanophotonics* **12**(8), 1405–1419 (2023).
4. R. Hekmati, J. P. Hadden, A. Mathew, S. G. Bishop, S. A. Lynch, and A. J. Bennett, "Bullseye dielectric cavities for photon collection from a surface-mounted quantum-light-emitter," *Sci Rep* **13**(1), 5316 (2023).
5. L. Sapienza, M. Davanço, A. Badolato, and K. Srinivasan, "Nanoscale optical positioning of single quantum dots for bright and pure single-photon emission," *Nat Commun* **6**(1), 7833 (2015).
6. M. Toda, "Single-mode behavior of a circular grating for potential disk-shaped DFB lasers," *IEEE Journal of Quantum Electronics* **26**(3), 473–481 (1990).
7. T. Erdogan and D. G. Hall, "Circularly symmetric distributed feedback semiconductor laser: An analysis," *Journal of Applied Physics* **68**(4), 1435–1444 (1990).
8. P. L. Greene and D. G. Hall, "Effects of radiation on circular-grating DFB lasers. I. Coupled-mode equations," *IEEE Journal of Quantum Electronics* **37**(3), 353–364 (2001).
9. J. Scheuer, W. M. J. Green, G. DeRose, and A. Yariv, "Annular Bragg defect mode resonators," in *Laser Resonators and Beam Control VII* (SPIE, 2004), **5333**, pp. 183–194.
10. J. Scheuer and A. Yariv, "Annular Bragg defect mode resonators," *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B, JOSAB* **20**(11), 2285–2291 (2003).
11. J. Scheuer, W. M. J. Green, G. A. DeRose, and A. Yariv, "InGaAsP annular Bragg lasers: theory, applications, and modal properties," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Quantum Electronics* **11**(2), 476–484 (2005).
12. Y. Wang, Z. Shi, X. Li, S. He, M. Zhang, and H. Zhu, "Surface-normal emission from subwavelength GaN membrane grating," *Opt. Express* **22**(1), 667 (2014).
13. L. Jin, X. Wang, L. Zeng, Z. Feng, N. Zhao, and X. Sun, "Etchless Dion–Jacobson–Phase Perovskite Surface-Emitting Circular Bragg Lasers with an Ultrahigh Q Factor," *ACS Photonics* **12**(1), 53–61 (2025).
14. S. Chu, A. Hayat, F. Cao, and T. Zhai, "Single-Mode Lasing in Polymer Circular Gratings," *Materials* **14**(9), 2318 (2021).
15. J. Huang, J. Mao, X. Li, J. Yuan, Y. Zheng, C. Zhai, T. Dai, Z. Fu, J. Bao, Y. Yang, D. Dai, Y. Li, Q. Gong, and J. Wang, "Integrated optical entangled quantum vortex emitters," *Nat. Photon.* **19**(5), 471–478 (2025).
16. G. Liang, H. Liang, Y. Zhang, S. P. Khanna, L. Li, A. Giles Davies, E. Linfield, D. Fatt Lim, C. Seng Tan, S. Fung Yu, H. Chun Liu, and Q. Jie Wang, "Single-mode surface-emitting concentric-circular-grating terahertz quantum cascade lasers," *Applied Physics Letters* **102**(3), 031119 (2013).
17. C. Guo, Z. Yang, W. Peng, S. Li, Z. Liu, Z. Liu, P. Yu, W. Wan, and X. Huang, "Improved optical performance in circular-grating distributed feedback nanoplasmonic lasers," *Optics Communications* **561**, 130513 (2024).
18. W. Wang, G. Zhu, Q. Liu, X. Li, T. Sa, X. Fang, H. Zhu, and Y. Wang, "Angle- and polarization-dependent spectral characteristics of circular grating filters," *Opt. Express* **24**(10), 11033 (2016).
19. C. R. Doerr and L. L. Buhl, "Circular grating coupler for creating focused azimuthally and radially polarized beams," *Opt. Lett.*, **OL 36**(7), 1209–1211 (2011).
20. Jacob Scheuer, William M.J. Green, and Amnon Yariv, "Annular Bragg Resonators: Beyond the Limits of Total Internal Reflection," https://www.photonics.com/Articles/Annular_Bragg_Resonators_Beyond_the_Limits_of/a21871.
21. A. Kitagawa and J. Sakai, "Bloch theorem in cylindrical coordinates and its application to a Bragg fiber," *Phys. Rev. A* **80**(3), 033802 (2009).
22. J. Scheuer and X. Sun, "Radial Bragg Resonators," in *Photonic Microresonator Research and Applications*, I. Chremmos, O. Schwelb, and N. Uzunoglu, eds. (Springer US, 2010), pp. 361–391.
23. J. Gu, X. Xi, J. Ma, Z. Yu, and X. Sun, "Parity–time-symmetric circular Bragg lasers: a proposal and analysis," *Sci Rep* **6**(1), 37688 (2016).
24. L. L. Sánchez-Soto, J. J. Monzón, A. G. Barriuso, and J. F. Cariñena, "The transfer matrix: A geometrical perspective," *Physics Reports* **513**(4), 191–227 (2012).
25. B. Zhou, X. Wang, Y. Zheng, X. Yu, J. Wang, Z. Sun, T. Xu, S. Xia, Y. Miao, P. Wen, K. Xiong, J. Liu, X. Zheng, H.-B. Wang, and H. Yang, "Inductively Coupled Plasma Etching of ITO Nanophotonic Structures for Visible Wavelengths," *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* **9**(1), 777–784 (2026).

26. Y. Zheng, Z. Sun, T. Xu, B. Zhou, X. Yu, X. Wang, J. Wang, Y. Miao, S. Xia, Z. Liu, Z. Li, P. Wen, K. Xiong, J. Liu, H. Wang, and H. Yang, "Low-threshold GaN surface emitting lasers: A comparative study of circular grating and photonic crystal designs," *J. Semicond.* **47**(5), 052504–6 (2026).
27. J. Wang, X. Wang, Y. Zheng, X. Yu, B. Zhou, Z. Sun, T. Xu, S. Xia, L. Sun, C. Guan, Y. Miao, P. Wen, C. Shen, K. Xiong, H. Wang, and H. Yang, "Investigating the Radial Photonic Band Structure of Second-Order Circular Gratings using FDTD and Hankel Transform," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Quantum Electronics* 1–11 (2026).